

Flexcrash

D2.1 Reliable process parameter sets for LMD

Project ref. no.	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-10 GA. N.º 101069674
Project title	Flexible and hybrid manufacturing of green aluminium to produce tailored adaptive crash-tolerant structures
Project duration	1 st September 2022 – 31 st August 2026 (48 months)
Related WP/Task	WP2 / T2.1
Dissemination level	Public
Document due date	31.08.2024
Actual delivery date	28/08/2024
Deliverable leader	Fraunhofer IWS
Document status	Submitted

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
1.0	01.08.2024	Eurecat	
1.1	14.08.2024	Fraunhofer IWS	
1.2	27.08.2024	Fraunhofer IWS	First completed version by deliverable responsible.
1.3	27.08.2024	EURECAT (Simona Neri)	Revision & Submission

Executive Summary

The document D2.1 “Reliable process parameter sets for LMD” collects the work performed by the Flexcrash consortium in Task 2.1 and is related to Key Exploitable Results (KER) 7 and 8, as listed below.

KER	Result	Category	Target groups	Exploitation route	IPR mechanism	Ownership
7	Advanced AM system technology for hybrid manufacturing and improved processing routes	Process	Industrial organizations, equipment manufacturers, research centers	Publications, training, consultancy, research	Copyright (for publications)	IWS
8	Development of deposition strategies for complex reinforcement structures manufactured by DED	Process	Industrial organizations, research centers	Publication, consultancy, research	Copyright (for publications) / other IPR mechanisms to be defined	IWS

This deliverable describes the technical challenge in the selection of the aluminium alloy, the DED-LB/P system and characteristics as well as the development of suitable process parameters and manufacturing strategies for reinforcement structures on thin metal sheets. Various factors influence the choices taken such as the availability of aluminium alloy powder in the market, thickness of the substrate material on top of which the reinforcement structures are deposited and maximum allowable thermal deformations.

The deliverable also highlights the common challenges of processing aluminium alloys with lasers, with a focus on both material quality assurance as well as obtainable geometrical accuracy of the manufactured parts. Several sensors-based solutions and feedforward- and feedback-controlling strategies are proposed in this deliverable to attenuate in the future the identified challenges and to increase the TRL of the technology to reach a system that can be used for series production in an industrial environment.

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Terminology and Acronyms

AM	Additive Manufacturing
CCD	Central Composite Design
DED-LB/P	Direct Energy Deposition with Laser Beam and Powder
DoE	Design of Experiments
EC	European Commission
EDX	Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
EU	European Union
FP	Framework Programme
LMD	Laser Metal Deposition (same as DED-LB/P from different nomenclature)
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

While the overall aims of the projects are to predict, design and manufacture reinforcement structures made of aluminium alloys by DED-LB/P on car body frames, this deliverable focuses on the development of the DED-LB/P processes to ensure quality and reproducibility of the obtained results on a lab-scale.

The optimal DED-LB/P process parameters to manufacture aluminium are highly dependent on the final geometry of the part, which influences the thermal dissipation capabilities from the melt pool. While bulky components allow more constant heat dissipation capability throughout the deposition, slender structures along the building direction are subjected to decreasing heat dissipation capabilities resulting in heat accumulation and longer solidification time of the melt pool.

A common strategy to develop DED-LB/P parameters consists of manufacturing single tracks on a substrate to identify the influence of the main process parameters on the geometry of the obtained tracks, mainly the track's width, height and penetration into the substrate (also called dilution). Afterwards, deposition of thin walls and volumes is performed to optimize the geometrical parameters, such as layer thickness and hatch distance between tracks within a layer. The combination of all process and geometrical parameters leads to unique material microstructures and properties that need to be investigated in order to perform the design of reinforcement structures.

2. Development of aluminium powder for Direct Energy Deposition

2.1 Material Selection

As specified in the proposal, new foundry SALEMA alloys with a reduced CRM content are selected as the initial material to produce Al powder for DED. The different alloys available for its selection are described in Table 1.

AlSi10Mg and AlSi8Mg were selected for the study. Moreover, based on IWS previous experience, they suggest adding 1%Zr to the desired alloys, as this element facilitates the nucleation of high melting point precipitates with a general grain refinement effect with a positive influence on both printability and mechanical properties of the alloy.

Table 1. Proposed alloys for additive manufacturing to be studied in the Flexcrash project

	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Zn	Ti	Ni	Pb	Sn
AlSi10Mg 3D Alchemy	9.0-11.0	<0.55	<0.08	<0.55	0.25-0.5	<0.15	<0.15	<0.15	<0.15	<0.05
Flexcrash green AlSi10Mg	9.0-11.0	<0.55	<0.15	<0.55	0.25-0.5	<0.25	<0.15	<0.05	<0.15	<0.05
Flexcrash green AlSi8Mg	7.0-9.0	<0.55	<0.15	<0.55	0.25-0.5	<0.25	<0.15	<0.05	<0.15	<0.05

+1% Zr

The initial test will be done using AlSi10Mg alloy with the corresponding addition of an Al-10%Zr master alloy. Based on the results and evolution of the project, the 2nd alloy using AlSi8Mg would be tested.

2.2 Powder production set-up process

Powder production was realized in the centrifugal atomization pilot plant developed at EURECAT. This section describes in chronological order the different iterations performed to obtain the desired powder with good quality in terms of chemical composition, morphology, and particle size distribution to fit the DED process. The different iterations are described as well as the results obtained in terms of metal powder characteristics. Finally, a summary of all tests is exposed in section 2.2.4 Summary of atomization test.

2.2.1 1st iteration test

Prior to the atomization process, billets with the desired chemical compositions are manufactured using initial AlSi10Mg alloy and Al-10%Zr master alloy. Raw materials are melted together in an aluminium melting furnace and poured into a mould to obtain the billets with the desired dimensions to fit into an atomizer crucible.

The atomization process and previous melting are performed in an N₂ inert gas atmosphere into an alumina crucible. Melt is atomized at 950°C using an atomization disc coated with ZrO₂ spinning at 35000 rpm. Selected parameters are based on previous experience atomizing Al alloy powders. The resulting powder was collected and sieved using 600, 150, 106 and 45 µm sieves.

Figure 1 shows an SEM image of the obtained powder in this trial test. The morphology of the powder is mainly spherical without satellites, which is the desired condition for the DED-LB/P process.

Figure 1. SEM results for 1st iteration test

A chemical analysis performed by ICP showed that Zr% content is significantly lower than expected. Results show that Zr content is 0.28%Zr, far from the expected 1%Zr. The same chemical analysis was performed directly on pieces of the initial billets used and results showed that the content %Zr of the billets is equal to the powder.

These results conclude that the melting strategy to manufacture the billets is not good, as Zr disappears, mainly due to oxidation of the Zr in the melting procedure. However, it is also verified that Zr% is not reduced in the second melting inside the atomizer, as this process is performed in an inert atmosphere.

2.2.2 2nd iteration test

Atomization adjusts the new chemical composition, adding to the pre-existent manufactured billets more Al-10%Zr master alloy in the corresponding proportions, to achieve desired composition. Atomization conditions were the same as in the 1st iteration test, but in this case, using Ar rather than N₂.

Figure 2 shows SEM images of the powder obtained. Figure 3 shows the EDX results to estimate the chemical composition of the powder.

Figure 2. SEM results for 2nd iteration test

Figure 3. SEM-EDX results for 2nd iteration test

Spectrum Label (%)	Spectrum 2	Spectrum 3	Spectrum 5	Spectrum 6
C	7,46	6,49		5,02
O	1,02	0,78		1,13
Mg			0,39	0,42
Al	79,14	83,39	90,25	80,2
Si	9,7	7,99	7,67	8,35
Mn	0,77	0,5	0,57	1,52
Fe	0,46	0,31	0,33	0,97
Zr	1,44	0,54	0,79	1,68

Table 2. SEM-EDX results for 2nd iteration test

EDX results show that, despite high variability in Zr% depending on the analyzed particle, an average of around 1%Zr was achieved. Other elements such Si, Mg, Mn or Fe are assumed to be in the acceptable range.

Compared to the 1st tests, the morphology of the powder has got worse, as particles are significantly more irregular. To improve this aspect other trials adjusting atomization process parameters are performed in the next stage.

2.2.3 3rd iteration test

Once the chemical composition is properly adjusted, the next step is to adjust process parameters to achieve spherical particles.

For these new atomization set-ups, melt temperature is changed while other process parameters are fixed. The first attempt was realized by increasing the melt temperature to 1100°C, which resulted in a worse performance of the atomization, with bad wettability of the molten metal onto the disc. The second attempt was performed at a lower temperature of 900°C. Results were positive in terms of the atomization performance, as in this case molten aluminium got well wetted into the atomization disc, obtaining a good yield of fine powder.

The reason for this change in the behavior is unknown although some hypotheses suggest that the wettability of the aluminium onto the disc and the surface tensions can change significantly at different temperatures. This can be a possible explanation, but further investigation of this aspect is out of the scope of this project.

Figure 4 shows the results of this second attempt which resulted in good yield. Details are shown in Table 5 in section 2.2.4 Summary of atomization test.

Figure 4. SEM results for 3rd iteration test

In this case, the powder obtained is highly spherical, better than previous atomization, indicating that good process parameters are achieved. EDX analysis in Figure 4 and Table 3 also show that the chemical composition is according to the desired.

Figure 5. SEM-EDX results for 3rd iteration test

Spectrum Label	Spectrum 7	Spectrum 8	Spectrum 9
Mg		0,47	
Al	87,05	87,74	87,12
Si	11,32	7,92	9,63
Mn	0,43	1,01	0,87
Fe	0,28	0,59	0,53
Zr	0,91	2,27	1,84
Total	100	100	100

Table 3. SEM-EDX results for 3rd iteration test

2.2.4 Summary of atomization test

Table 4 shows a summary of all atomization tests performed with the process parameters and Table 5 shows the results of the powder obtained, indicating the yield of each fraction.

Table 4. Process parameters of each atomization and general comments

At. Num.	Quantity (gr)	Temperature (C°)	Speed (rpm)	Gas
1	900gr [AlSi10Mg] + 100gr [M.A. Al10%Zr]	905	42000	N ₂
2	928,3gr [AlSi10Mg+1%Zr]	905	36000	N ₂
3	930,6gr [AlSi10Mg+1%Zr]	905	36000	N ₂

4	929gr [AlSi10Mg+1%Zr]	905	36000	N ₂
5	801,9gr [AlSi10Mg+0.25%Zr] + 65,2gr [M.A. Al10%Zr]	950	40000	Ar
6	801,9gr [AlSi10Mg+0.25%Zr] + 65,2gr [M.A. Al10%Zr]	1100	37000	Ar
7	657gr [AlSi10Mg+0.25%Zr] + 53,7gr [M.A. Al10%Zr]	900	37000	Ar
8	659,7gr [AlSi10Mg+0.25%Zr] + 53,6gr [M.A. Al10%Zr]	900	37000	Ar
9	657,9gr [AlSi10Mg+0.25%Zr] + 53,8gr [M.A. Al10%Zr]	900	37000	Ar

Table 5. Summary of the powder quantities obtained in each atomization

At. Num.	Quantity obtained by granulometry (g)				Total mass (g)	Efficiency (%) <45 µm
	600-150 µm	150-106 µm	106-45 µm	<45 µm		
1	46,84	63,77	145,78	15,58	271,96	5,73
2	48,63	347,51	267,21	7,58	670,93	1,13
3	34,78	571,31	91,86	5,87	703,82	0,83
4	338,29	60,70	98,02	7,86	504,87	1,56
5	142,06	77,62	140,42	8,82	368,92	2,39
6	97,46*				97,46	0
7	87,92	184,35	253,32	12,08	537,67	2,25
8	127,09	139,64	228,98	10,86	506,57	2,14
9	135,08	154,62	210,63	11,24	511,57	2,20

* Not sieved due to unsatisfactory results (bad wettability of the melt onto the disc).

2.3 Conclusions in atomization process

Several conclusions can be drawn from the atomization carried out and collected in Table 4. First of all, the effect of the melting temperature should be highlighted. It was observed that the lower the melting temperature before atomization, the higher the amount of fine powder fraction produced. The powder obtained from the atomization at 1100°C was the one with the highest coarse fraction of all the runs. Therefore, it was decided to reduce to 950°C, still without obtaining the desired result, and finally to 900°C, where higher yields of fine powder were obtained, maybe due to a better wettability of the molten aluminium at this temperature on the atomization disc. No lower temperatures are tested to avoid the solidification of the molten aluminium on the atomization disc that could cause unwanted effects.

Regarding the morphology, it was observed that the powder produced in the first iteration test was the most spherical compared to the 2nd and 3rd iterations. The Zr percentage of the atomization in the 1st iteration was lower than in the following iterations, and that could be the reason for the observed results, as Zr seems to obstruct particle spheroidization. 2nd iteration contained oval-shaped particles and in the 3rd iteration solidified metal debris was observed on the disc. One possible answer to these results is the reduction in melting temperature. Atomizing the material at a lower temperature makes it easier to solidify the material on the disc surface and produce the debris found in the powder. One point to note is that the powder obtained in these three iterations shares the non-existence of satellites.

Regarding the composition, we could see through the EDX analysis how the percentage of Zr in the powder increased for the 2nd and 3rd iterations. In other words, there was a correlation between the increase of Zr in the ingots used in the 2nd and 3rd iterations and the Zr content present in that powder with respect to the powder produced in the 1st iteration where the raw composition contained less Zr.

As a summary of the amount of powder obtained from the iterations performed, a total amount of 1,6 kg of powder with particle size between 150-106µm and 1,4 kg of particle size between 106-45 µm were produced.

3. Development of DED-LB/P process parameters for AlSi10Mg

3.1 Used equipment and fixed parameters

Flexcrash ambition is to increase the front structure crashworthiness of car body frames while keeping the part lightweight and sustainable to produce. The aim is to achieve this increase by applying reinforcement structures made of aluminium alloy by DED technology onto existing designs the tailor the mechanical properties and the energy absorption of the deforming part in case of a crash.

The application of reinforcement structure by DED onto thin frames used as a substrate is challenging since the thermal properties of DED processes induce thermal deformations and stresses. DED by means of a laser beam and powder material was chosen as technology since it is the DED process with the highest capabilities in terms of energy input control. Processing aluminium alloys by means of a laser, especially in the case of AM applications, presents different challenges:

- Need for an inert atmosphere around the processing zone for safety reasons

- High hydrogen solubility in molten aluminium results in gas pores formation during the solidification phase of the process
- Oxygen solubility leads to the formation of oxides on top of the melt pool leading to lower surface tension and unknown interaction method with the subsequent layer leading to the formation of defects
- Low absorption coefficient of aluminium alloys to infrared wavelengths of the processing laser
- Low melting temperature leads to a long solidification time of the melt pool, which has time to spread on a thin and wide track.

Figure 6 Used industrial DED-LB/P equipment. Left: Machine with inert atmosphere capabilities. Right: Deposition head with laser-powder nozzle

Due to the above-mentioned challenges, it was decided to use the industrial DED-LB/P system BeAM Magic 800, which is capable of creating an inert atmosphere ($O_2 < 50 \text{ ppm}$, $H_2O < 100 \text{ ppm}$) within the entire working space of the machine and it is equipped with a laser source and deposition head with the following characteristics and parameters:

Table 6 List of characteristics and fixed parameters used in the DED-LB/P system

Max laser power	1000 W	Carrier gas	3 l/min Ar
Laser wavelength	1070 nm	Shielding gas	3 l/min Ar
Laser spot	0.8 mm	Forming gas	6 l/min Ar
Powder PSD	45-105 μm	Powder spot	0.8 mm

The selected system and parameters allow for minimization of the thermal input of the process onto the substrate material, preventing the need for excessive clamping and active cooling systems on the substrate to avoid perforation and melting of the thin metal sheets.

3.2 Single tracks and parameters influence

The usually adopted procedure to develop process parameters for DED-LB/P technology for a specific material-system combination consists of:

1. Deposition of single tracks with varying main parameters to understand the influence of such parameters on the obtained track's geometry
2. Selection of process parameters to match the desired minimum deposition rate while keeping material quality requirements and a deposited track with an aspect ratio of height/width between 1/3 and 1/4.
3. Deposition of volumes with geometry resembling the final application to develop the geometrical parameters of hatch distance between tracks in one layer and layer thickness.
4. Iterative optimization to achieve desired material quality and geometrical accuracy of the manufactured volumes

A DoE with CCD distribution was chosen having the ideal amount of runs with accurate quadratic model interpolation of the parameters influence on the track's geometry. The identified main process parameters to vary during the study are laser power, scanning speed and powder feed rate. For the first iteration, these ranges for each continuous factor were used:

Table 7 Used parameters in the first iteration

Laser power	700 – 900 W
Scanning speed	1300 – 1700 mm/min
Powder feed rate	1.7 – 2.3 g/min

Results, as visible in Figure 7 and Figure 8, show the effects of each varied process parameter on the track's geometry and two significant cross-sections from the DoE respectively. Although the results show a clear influence (p-value < 0.05) of laser power and scanning speed on the obtained track width and of powder feed rate on the obtained track height, none of the tracks satisfied all requirements of material quality and geometry aspect ratio at the same time. Therefore, a second iteration with a modified parameters range was performed:

Table 8 Used parameters in the second iteration

Laser power	500 – 700 W
Scanning speed	1000 – 1500 mm/min
Powder feed rate	1.3 – 1.7 g/min

Figure 7 Main effect plots of first parameters iteration

Figure 8 Metallographic investigation of two tracks from the first parameters iteration

Results visible in Figure 9 and Figure 10 as well as the detailed ANOVA tables in Table 9 and Table 10 point out the significant influence of laser power on the width of the track and of scanning speed and powder feed rate on the height. Moreover, due to the application on thin substrates, the penetration of the melt pool into the substrate (also called dilution) was measured and laser power proved to be the only significant factor. In Figure 10 three different cross-sections of tracks with different parameters are shown, pointing out the difference in obtained aspect ratio and material quality throughout the second iteration of the DoE. Amongst these results, the process parameters of laser power 600 W, speed 1250 mm/min and powder feed rate of 1.5 g/min were chosen as ideal ones to achieve the desired combination of material quality and aspect ratio close to 1/4.

Figure 9 Main effect plots of second parameters iteration

Figure 10 Metallographic investigation of 3 significant tracks during the second parameters iteration

Table 9 ANOVA table of the second DoE showing the presence of two significant factors for the obtained track height

ANOVA - Height (mm)						
Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F value	P value	Significance
Model	9	0.025415	0.002824	12.27	0.002	x

Lp	1	0.000142	0.000142	0.62	0.458	
ν	1	0.021255	0.021255	92.36	0	x
pfr	1	0.002865	0.002865	12.45	0.01	x
Lp*Lp	1	0.000019	0.000019	0.08	0.783	
$\nu*\nu$	1	0.000703	0.000703	3.05	0.124	
pfr*pfr	1	0.000086	0.000086	0.38	0.559	
Lp* ν	1	0.00005	0.00005	0.22	0.767	
Lp*pfr	1	0.000144	0.000144	0.63	0.655	
$\nu*pfr$	1	0.000072	0.000072	0.31	0.454	
Error	7	0.001611	0.00023	0.593		
Total	16	0.027026				
Model Summary						
S	R-sq [%]	R-sq(adj) [%]	R-sq(pred) [%]			
0.01517	94.04	86.38	61.8			

Table 10 ANOVA table of the second DoE showing the presence of only one significant factor for the obtained track width

ANOVA - Height (mm)						
Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F value	P value	Significance
Model	9	0.017156	0.001906	4.66	0.027	
Lp	1	0.014305	0.014305	34.97	0.001	x
ν	1	0.000015	0.000015	0.04	0.852	
pfr	1	0.001294	0.001294	3.16	0.118	
Lp*Lp	1	0.000195	0.000195	0.48	0.512	
$\nu*\nu$	1	0.000032	0.000032	0.08	0.789	
pfr*pfr	1	0.000443	0.000443	1.08	0.333	
Lp* ν	1	0	0	0	0.987	
Lp*pfr	1	0.000528	0.000528	1.29	0.293	
$\nu*pfr$	1	0.000105	0.000105	0.26	0.628	
Error	7	0.002863	0.000409			
Total	16	0.02002				
Model Summary						
S	R-sq [%]	R-sq(adj) [%]	R-sq(pred) [%]			
0.020225	85.7	67.31	0			

3.3 Thin walls deposition strategy

With most materials and alloys, only small adjustments of the process parameters are needed going from single tracks to volumes and these are usually identified only by the presence of pores or lack of fusion defects. In the case of aluminium alloys, on the other hand, also the obtained geometrical accuracy plays a significant role. While manufacturing thin wall structures to optimize the programmed layer thickness, it became clear that after only a few couples of layers, the slender structure changes the boundary conditions of the process enough to obtain a completely different cross-section of the track. As visible in Figure 12, the upper layers are significantly wider and thinner with respect to the first one.

Figure 11 Schematic representation of the geometrical parameters in DED processes

Figure 12 Initial results obtained during thin walls geometrical parameters development. In the image on the right, the widening effect of the melt pool is visible by the eyes.

Because of the results obtained, it became clear the need to develop also a deposition strategy to obtain more uniform walls with expected final cross-sectional dimensions of 2 mm in width and 2.5 mm in height. As visible in Figure 13, the developed strategy to obtain a wall with uniform width consists of 3 equally spaced tracks in the first layer with a bidirectional deposition strategy, 2 tracks in the second layer and a single track from the third layer on. Although this strategy allowed the manufacturing of walls with a relatively uniform 2 mm width while keeping a low dilution of the reinforcement material into the substrate, the presence of occasional lateral sprays of material from the melt pool remains visible due to the overheating of the molten aluminium. The obtained walls were however considered good enough to induce a reinforcement on the applied substrate and the repeatable results showed promising possibility of industrialization of the technology.

Figure 13 Left: Obtained thin wall with the use of two tracks in the first layer. Center: Defined deposition strategy for the uniform wall. Right: Uniform wall thickness with visible lateral spray of the melt pool.

Moreover, in order to allow the design of more complex reinforcement structures, the deposition strategy for crossing walls was also investigated. As visible in Figure 14, with a programmed distance between the walls equal to half the value of the hatch spacing, it was possible to manufacture crossing walls which showed only the presence of one lack of fusion defect between the first two deposited layers, but with an overall acceptable quality.

Figure 14 Left: Top view of manufactured T crossing between two walls. Right: Metallographic investigation of crossing walls

3.4 Conclusion of the DED-LB/P development

The developed process parameters and strategies for the DED-LB/P of AlSi10Mg reinforcements on thin metal sheets pointed out that:

- Reinforcement structures can be manufactured by DED-LB/P on a 1.5 mm thick substrate without excessive thermal deformation.

- The cross-sectional area of the reinforcement walls was limited to 2 mm in width and 2.5 mm in height to prevent excessive deformation of the substrate and weight addition.
- A deposition strategy which depends on a predefined cross-sectional area must be developed to obtain acceptable geometrical accuracy and material quality
- The reinforcement capabilities depend on the mechanical properties of the DED-LB/P deposited material, which in turn depends on the obtained material quality and microstructure in the geometry. Testing of the reinforcements directly instead of samples extracted from large volumes is considered fundamental prior to the design phase of complex reinforcements.